

EARTH SCIENCES

THE ORIGIN OF OIL AND GAS FIELDS

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Abstract

In modern science, there are 2 hypotheses of the origin of oil and gas: organic and inorganic. Organic matter dominates - oil and gas are considered to be the decomposition product of organic substances that lived on Earth millions of years ago. The formation of deposits is represented as a slow process of replacement of water molecules in the reservoir by hydrocarbon molecules inflowing from outside.

I believe that all oil and gas deposits were formed as a result of the eruption of hydrocarbons from under the foundation of the earth's crust. In this article, I shared the evidence for my hypothesis.

Keywords: oilfields, gaz, origin, organic, inorganic, volcanic, eruption, mantle, earthquake, hydrocarbon.

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I would like to remind the readers that there is no general conception of oil and gas genesis in modern science. There are two hypotheses of their genesis — organic and inorganic. The organic concept dominates in oil geology, its main point is that oil and gas resulted from the decomposition of organic matter existed on Earth by a millions years ago.

As for process of oil and gas fields origin, the geologists have one notion. This is a slow substitution of water molecules from formation by hydrocarbon molecules flowing from outside. I am presenting my own hypothesis of oil and gas fields genesis and I talk about it as a discovery because I sure in truly of it.

I believe that all of oil and gas fields have originated as result of hydrocarbons eruption from under the base of the earth crust with further filling various underground collectors.

This theory is proved by following facts:

1 fact. The conformity of the earth crust elevation in multilayered oil fields along the vertical to the earth surface (Figures №1 and №2). This is the result of vertical volcanic eruption of hydrocarbons with further extrusion of water out of collectors and distribution according to the density of hydrocarbons [1].

These elevations start from the base, and in some oilfields they rise to the surface, reflecting structural features of oil saturated beds (Sutorminskoye, Aganskoye, Chernogorskoye elevations of Samotlor oilfield etc.). As result of conformable elevation, the hills are formed in above listed oilfields.

Why "volcanic"? Because volcanoes are eruptions of hydrocarbons followed by magmatic lava of such force that they could reach the surface of the earth. It is known that during the volcano eruption a lot of gas is discharged, but you could ask about where is the oil here?

Gas, getting in contact with air, explodes, which is usually the case during the volcano action. So, what about oil? Oil burns out during the eruption evolving black or grey smoke (photo of volcanic eruptions) mixed with steam of water occurred in volcano crater. Look at the photos and, if you ever saw oil burning (photo of burning oil), you would agree that the smoke coming from volcano crater is identical to the one evolving while burning oil.

Volcanoes that haven't reached the earth's surface create oil and gas fields. This underground volcanic activity is apparently the cause of the earthquakes. Vertically directed eruption creates the earthquake focus. Current seismically active regions and active volcanoes are the relief points of overpressure created by hydrocarbons being continuously formed under the base of the earth crust.

Translation:
 Система- **Structure**
 Отдел – **Series**
 Ярус – **Stage**
 Формация – **Formation**
 Глубина, м – **Depth, m**
 Приобское – **Priobskoye**
 Приразломное – **Prirazlomnoye**
 Салымское – **Salymskoye**
 Меловая – **Cretaceous**
 Юрская – **Jurassic**
 Палеозой – **Palaeozoic**
 Фроловская – **Frolovskaya**
 Тюменская – **Tyumenskaya**
 Фундамент - **Base**

Figure № 1. Fragment of geological section on latitudinal Priobye.

Translation:
 Породы коллектора, заполненные водой – **Water saturated reservoir rocks**
 Породы непроницаемые для газов и жидкостей – **Gas and fluid impermeable rocks**
 Газ – **Gas**
 Нефть – **Oil**
 Море – **Sea**
 Осадочный слой – **Sedimentary**
 Фундамент – **Base**
 Слой Гутенберга – **Gutenberg layer**
 Мантия - **Mantle**

Figure № 2. Simplified earth structure down to the base and under it prior to and after hydrocarbons eruption.

Photos of volcanic eruptions

Photos of burning oil

Figure №3 shows the compound seismic section based on data obtained having carried out geology-geophysical surveys in the area of Spitak earthquake focus [2]. Abnormality zone (bright green spot), featuring low seismic waves speed, high apparent specific resistance of $50000 \text{ ohm} \cdot \text{m}$, located in the hypocenter of Spitak earthquake, can be quite explained, assuming it to be the hydrocarbons accumulation (mostly gas – the resistance is very high) resulted from the blowout. I am

sure that such “abnormality spot” could be found under the focus of each noted and quite powerful earthquake.

Once I. Kant noted "A country can be saved from fierce earthquakes when a volcano starts being active nearby. Therefore, what horrifies us can quite often bring us good". In other words, the German philosopher noticed interrelation and common cause of these natural phenomena. And Japanese worship their famous Fujiyama volcano not in vain. Had it not relieved the extra force of underground thrusts, number of casualties during earthquakes would have been much greater.

Рис. 3. Сводный сейсмический разрез по профилю Армаш - Ахалцихе:

Translation:

Закавказская микроплита – **Trans-Caucasian shield**

Центрально-Армянская Аккреционная зона – **Central Armenian Accretion zone**

Южно-Армянская микроплита – **Southern Armenian shield**

СЗ – **NW**

Ширакская зона – **Shirak zone**

ЮВ - **SE**

Сводный сейсмический разрез по профилю Армаш-Ахалцихе – **The composite seismic cross section along Armash-Akhaltikhe profile**

2 fact. Abnormally low and high pressure occur in the oilfield depending on whether the part of hydrocarbons have blown out to the upper beds and to the surface or not. Abnormally low-pressure results from the migration of hydrocarbons along remained or newly formed channels.

Abnormally high pressure occurs when lithology closed collectors either natural or formed as result of a fault are filled. The fault (fracture) originates under pressure of erupting hydrocarbons because of elevation unconformity as consequence of upper beds inflexibility.

A well-known throttle effect (Joule-Thomson effect), gas adiabatic expansion resulting in lowering temperature could be the cause of mammoths being suddenly frozen. And consequently expansion of great volume of gas became the prime cause of the glacial epoch to come.

3 fact. Elongation of each oil and gas field having water-oil contact to a definite side (in West Siberia – from South to North, in Kazakhstan – from East to West and so forth) , which is the result of hydrocarbons spreading and extruding formation water along the least resistance – to neighboring seas and oceans (to Arctic ocean and to Caspian sea).

One of the consequences of the extrusion was “The Flood”, and indeed so was the Flood origin described in the Bible.

The disappearance of Aral Sea and started shallowing of Balkhash lake could be connected to the development of hydrocarbon fields located nearby. The quantity of produced oil is equal to the quantity of disappeared water.

4 fact. “Dragon”, “White Tiger” and other Vietnamese fields located in rocks of base are resulted from

Bitumen

7 fact. Higher temperatures of oil and gas fields [4] compared with the background in the region can be explained by assumption that the flow of hydrocarbons into formations was nearly immediate. Hotter hydrocarbons going upward did not have time to cool down.

8 fact. Dark color of basalt, current construction material for lower layers of the earth crust, is caused by mixing of mantle matter with black hydrocarbons (oil), which in its turn are accumulated in upper layers of asthenosphere (in mantle upper layer).

The proof of existing hydrocarbons under the base could be the Gutenberg layer, the uppermost layer of

hydrocarbon eruptions and filling by hydrocarbons the interstices of rocks which constitute the base.

To explain the fact of oil existing in the base rocks the organic oil genesis theory advocates had to set up a hypothesis that significant formation pressure could direct oil migration down. I think that filling the interstices of rocks by hydrocarbons going from under the base is more logical and does not require applying higher mathematics.

5 fact. Offshore fields out in the seas and oceans are also originated in result of hydrocarbon eruptions. Offshore fields are known to be poorly explained by the organic oil genesis hypothesis. The above stated theory allows the possibility of the oil fields to exist almost under any earth and sea surface.

6 fact. Black coal was formed by lithification of bitumen remained after light hydrocarbons escaped from the oil erupted to the surface. Suffice it to look into the reference book to be certain in almost identical content of oil and black coal, and also, if you break off a piece of coal and bitumen and look at similar color and flash of both pieces. So coal has been formed not from the organic remains of flora and fauna, extinct millions years ago, but from oil erupted to the surface and not burnt.

The main argument of coal organic origin is the prints of plants and plants themselves extinct many millions years ago. But the reason they remained is because they have been covered by oil and so preserved.

Brown coal is probably the only organic remains of plants existed many years ago, and in considerable part it is mixed with oil and other rocks (sand, clay etc.). Athabasca bitumen field in Canada being developed as an open pit is an example of the incompletely formed coalfield.

Coal

asthenosphere, characterized by low spread velocity seismic waves. Assuming that this layer consists mostly of gas accumulating under the earth crust, and then we can expect the lower velocity seismic waves in this layer.

Discovery of hydrocarbons origin became the guiding thread, which brought me not only to understanding of earthquakes and earth volcanic activity origin, but also to understanding of many processes taking place on earth and other planets. But that will be the subject of further articles.

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HEAVENS

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Abstract

Let's turn to Heavens. The knowledges that we have today and, the most important, the conclusions that we have drawn from them and pass them off as truth, are well known to everyone.

The main tool that gives astronomers information about "endless" space of the Universe and what is in – it's a telescope. As more powerful telescope we have as farther we see. And, accordingly, if we don't see the body (star) in a smaller telescope and see in a larger one, then this body (star) is further away.

The Quran says that God made Heavens out of seven sky's and put the stars on the first from us. Therefore, it's logically to assume that in telescopes we see the "bottom" of this first sky, and the more powerful the telescope the more detailed it shows "this sole". This is my assumption.

Keywords: heavens, light, origin, space, telescope, astronomers, universe, Hubble, probes, stars.

"He is The One who created everything on the Earth for us, then He turned to the Heavens and built it from the seven skys. He knows everything!"

Let's turn to Heavens too. The knowledges that we have today and, the most important, the conclusions that we have drawn from them and pass them off as truth, are well known to everyone. Let's analyze where we got and get any knowledges about structure and size of the Universe?

The main tool that gives astronomers information about "endless" space of the Universe and what is in – it's a telescope. Increasing the resolution of the telescope we "looking deep into the Universe." We think so.

Lets answer to the question about difference between a microscope and a telescope[1]. They differ in two things - in size and in tasks. But their principle of action is the same - to increase and approximate. When we look through a microscope and explore what is in focus, we understand that we are considering the detailed structure of the body we are studying. And as

more magnifying microscope we take as smaller "details" of the body we can see.

With a telescope we have completely different idea. As more powerful telescope we have as farther we see. And, accordingly, if we don't see the body (star) in a smaller telescope and see in a larger one, then this body (star) is further away.

The Quran [2] says that God made Heavens out of seven sky's and put the stars on the first from us.

Therefore, it's logically to assume that in telescopes we see the "bottom" of this first sky, and the more powerful the telescope the more detailed it shows "this sole". This is an assumption, what evidence is available. Let's try to analyze it.

1. Hubble telescope [3]. This telescope was built to "look into the past". At the time of its creation (according to scientists) size and age of the universe was 7-10 billion years. Hubble had to look further than these 10 billion years and show what happened in the Universe immediately after the Big Bang. With Hubble we saw the same stars (stellar systems) that we saw and explored before. Therefore, this telescope increased the age of the Universe to 13-15 billion years. To look further, it is necessary to build more powerful telescope - scientists think so. I'm sure the next telescope will show what happened before the Big Bang. And the next one even more. And so it will be to infinity.

2. The American space probes Pioneer 10 and Pioneer 11 were launched in 1972 and 1973. By now, they should have already left the solar system. However, both - first and second - for unknown reasons changed their trajectory, as if an unknown force didn't let them out of the system. Pioneer 10 has already deviated by four hundred thousand kilometers from the calculated trajectory. Pioneer 11 exactly follows the path of its predecessor. There are many versions: the influence of the solar wind, fuel leakage, programming